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GEN Z COLLEGE STUDENTS' PERCEPTION ON HISTORICAL EPICS: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL STUDY

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Abstract

This qualitative study examines the perception of college students in the digital age on the Philippine historical epics. This research is anchored on Schema Theory (Anderson, 2010) and Prensky's (2001) Digital Natives Theory, examining the impact of knowledge and digital preferences frameworks on students' receptivity to traditional narratives. According to recent studies, such as Ong and Cabañero (2021), Philippine curriculum literature is the link between national norms and cultural identity. Peñalba et al. (2020) demonstrated how digital storytelling may be used as instructional material to foster cultural awareness. The impact of digitalization on cultural preservation and identity must be explored, as there exists very limited localized research on how Gen Z Filipinos use digital media to consume historical epics.

A phenomenological study was employed using purposive sampling, and six students from Abuyog Community College were interviewed face-to-face using semi-structured interview guides. Results show formal education introduced these works, alongside other epics, through the reading of textbooks, lectures, and classroom discussions. This reflects Ong and Cabañero's (2021) view that literature in the curriculum transmits cultural identity and values.

The results indicate that YouTube and TikTok offer more engaging and accessible content about historical epics for Gen Z college students. Findings suggest that students view digital media as a modern pedagogical tool that effectively stimulates interest and appreciation for cultural heritage, bridging traditional teaching methods with contemporary digital experiences. While some participants still value traditional approaches, the majority show enthusiasm for digital storytelling tailored to their generation. Integrating various media formats in teaching Philippine historical epics has proven effective in keeping cultural identity relevant and resonant with Gen Z learners.

Keywords: Gen Z , historical Epics, cultural identity, digital age , college students

Introduction

The rise of social media has transformed access to information, offering a wide range of applications and easy access to content. This digital revolution has greatly shaped Generation Z, those born between 1997 and 2012, who are considered "digital natives." As the Pew Research Center (2019) describes, they are growing up in a "deeper web" of technology, making their worldview more global and digitally oriented.

In contrast, Philippine historical epics were traditionally passed down orally from one generation to the next. According to Santos (2008), works such as *Biag ni Lam-ang*, *Hudhud*, and *Darangen* serve not only as stories but also as vessels of memory, values, and identity. However, Gen Z's heavy exposure to digital technology raises questions about how they connect with and

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engage in these traditional narratives. While research has examined the role of digital media in shaping reading culture, few localized studies have explored how Filipino Gen Z learners interpret historical epics in the digital context.

In the same manner, if Generation Z had the absence or fail to take into their own these epics, then it is very likely that such cultural treasures will be thrown away to a fate that will probably mean the disintegration of the national identity and continuity. Peñalba et al. (2020) has warned that, without such innovative approaches, the classic texts are most likely going to become irrelevant to present-day learners. Further Tolentino (2014) added that digital media have that great potential of bridging the gap between culture and technology, making the works relevant. The works of Botangen, Vodanovich, and Yu (2018) demonstrated the potential of social media in the preservation of indigenous culture and suggested that a lack of responsiveness may exacerbate cultural disconnection.

Given this context, it discusses the current study's exploration of Gen Z's perceptions of Philippine historical epics, as well as their applicability and online consumption. This looks at whether the works are getting less popular or changing as new ones come out. The study also tries to get Gen Z involved in keeping Filipino historical epics alive in the digital age, so these stories continue to help build Filipino identity. The research intends to pinpoint processes that sustain appreciation for these epics and show how modern technology might be employed for their ongoing relevance by capturing the ways in which students interact with culture and tradition.

Statement of the Problem

This study explores on the Generation Z college students on Philippine Historical. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions.

1. How do Gen Z students describe their awareness and understanding of Philippine historical epics?
2. In what ways are these epics being introduced and accessed by students in an educational and digital environment?
3. How do digital platforms (e.g., social media, videos, gamified content) influence the perceptions of Gen Z students engage on Philippine Epics?
4. How do Gen Z college students perceive Philippine Historical Epics in Digital Platforms?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

To determine and analyze the perception of Generation Z in Philippine Historical Epics, qualitative phenomenological approach was employed. This design according to Cresswell (2013) is then fitting because it focuses on the meaning of lived experiences and how an individual perceives and makes use of the phenomena. In this case, how Gen Z perceives historical epics.

The design involves depth interviews or open-ended questionnaire to collect rich, detailed subjective data about participants' perspective.

Research Instrument and Validation

The research instrument is a semi-structured interview guide aimed at gathering insights from Generation Z students about their perception on Philippine historical epics in the digital era. It features open-ended questions exploring their perceptions, understanding, and digital access to epics such as Biag ni Lam-ang, Hudhud ni Aliguyon, and Darangen. The guide also examines the impact of digital platforms on their engagement and appreciation of these traditional narratives. Interviews was conducted in a quiet environment and recorded, with participants' consent for subsequent analysis.

To guarantee the validity of the study, the research adviser thoroughly reviewed the instrument, guaranteeing the interview questions matched the goals and problem statement of the study, and were acceptable.

Locale of the Study

The study was carried out at Abuyog Community College (ACC) and focused only on Gen Z students enrolled in the current academic year. ACC was chosen because it is a community-based institution that brings together students from diverse backgrounds. This setting allowed the researchers to easily reach participants and capture the perspectives of provincial college students navigating the digital age.

Participants Selection and Sampling

To select participants who meet specific criteria purposive sampling was used. The inclusion criteria were (i) currently enrolled in the institutions across different courses. (ii) must be born from 1997 onwards.

Characteristics of the Participants

Participant's Code	Program	Sex	Age
Participant 1	BSCRIM	Female	22
Participant 2	BEED	Female	20
Participant 3	BSED	Male	19
Participant 4	BSIT	Female	22
Participant 5	BSHM	Male	23
Participant 6	BSENTREP	Female	20

Data Analysis

The interviews data were carefully transcribed and thoroughly reviewed by repeatedly reading the transcripts. During coding, key ideas and recurring phrases were identified and consistently categorized across participants. These codes were then grouped into broader themes that capture shared experiences and perspectives. The themes were rigorously evaluated for consistency and relevance to the study objectives, and clearly defined to accurately represent the main insights from the diverse student participants.

Data Collection Process

To show respect and professionalism, the researchers asked permission from the college president to interview Gen Z college students within the campus, Semi-structured interviews were conducted with all participants, and the responses were later examined using Braun and Clarke's (2006) thematic analysis framework. During the interviews, data saturation was carefully monitored to determine the point at which no new insights or themes appeared, signaling the conclusion of data gathering. This method allowed for a thorough exploration of participants' perspectives and strengthening both the credibility and richness of the phenomenological approach

Ethical Considerations

This study strictly follows ethical guidelines by obtaining permission from the school administration and securing informed consent from all participants. Participation was voluntary, with the right to withdraw at any time without penalty. Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained, and all data were used exclusively for academic purposes. The research ensured that no physical, psychological, or emotional harm occurred to participants throughout the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following themes emerged after a thorough **analyzation** of gathered data.

Awareness and Understanding

The respondents' awareness of Philippine historical epics is generally **partial and limited to the most well-known stories** such as *Biag ni Lam-ang* and *Hudhud*. As it was being taught to them in their high school year. This was evident in the response of Participant 1 who stated *"I am pretty familiar with the Philippines historical epic specifically Biag ni Lam-ang. I have learned about this epic in School. It was discussed during our Filipino Subject. Philippines Historical Epic specifically, Biag ni Lam-ang brought an impact and significance to better understand our Filipino History and Identity, in this way we could learn and imagine what it looked like during that time. To better understand the characters or attitude a Filipino Citizen must have"*. Similar responses were noted from three participants, including Participants 3, 4, and 5. This statement reflects how formal education remains the primary channel for introducing students to epics. It aligns with Ong and Cabañero (2021), who emphasized that Philippine literature in the curriculum plays a crucial role in transmitting cultural identity and national values among learners. Similarly, schema theory (Anderson, 2010) supports this observation, suggesting that prior knowledge frameworks—such as classroom instruction—shape how students interpret and retain narratives. In this case, the participant's understanding of *Biag ni Lam-ang* was scaffolded by the structured discussions in school, highlighting the enduring role of education in cultural transmission despite the distractions of the digital age. However, Participant 2 admitted that *"I'm not very familiar with all the epics, pero nakabati na ak san hud-hud ngan biag ni lam-ang. When I first heart it sugad an mga adventure story la gihapon. For me, importanti ini Kay Filipino epics shows our Filipino history ngansin an atun identity, sugad an mga roots natun as a nation"*. ("I'm not very familiar with all the epics, but I've encountered the Hudhud and Biag ni Lam-ang. When I first heard them, they

seemed just like adventure stories. For me, these are important because Filipino epics show our history and our identity, like the roots of our nation.”) Similar responses were noted from participant 6 who also shared that they had partial and limited familiarity regarding to Philippine historical epics.

Introduced in School-Access Now on the Internet

Participants dominant response, it was introduced first in school through school curriculum and traditional ways. However, nowadays it can be access in different social media platforms such as TikTok and YouTube. Based on the interview, the answer of participant 4 best captured, who stated that *“Yes nadiscuss ini Siya sa klase, pero mostly through textbooks, mga lecture, ngansin medyo boring Siya usahay Kay puro la baya adtu Siya basa. I also saw some epics, an sa TikTok mayda na baya gihap situn, sa YouTube, ngan iba na mga websites, mga animated version San biag ni lam- ang or an hud-hud na mas engaging. I think, kulang pa an schools in introducing epics damo pa mga students na waray pagud appreciation san importance san mga epics”*. (“Yes, this was discussed in class, but mostly through textbooks and lectures, and sometimes it gets a bit boring since it’s all just reading. I also saw some epics on TikTok, YouTube, and other websites—like animated versions of Biag ni Lam-ang or Hudhud—which are more engaging. I think schools are still lacking in how they introduce epics, since many students don’t yet have an appreciation for their importance.”) This perspective reflects **Prensky’s (2001) Digital Natives Theory**, which argues that learners of the digital generation prefer interactive and media-rich formats over traditional text-based instruction. Likewise, **Greenhow, Robelia, and Hughes (2009)** highlight that social media platform serve as informal learning spaces that enhance engagement, especially for younger learners who are accustomed to fast, visual, and participatory forms of content. In line with this, a study by **Cayubit (2020)** on Filipino students’ learning engagement found that digital and multimedia resources increase interest and comprehension compared to traditional lecture-based methods.

Digital Influence

Digital platforms greatly influence how Gen Z students engage with Philippine historical epics, making the stories more lively, engaging, and accessible. Participants see these platforms as tools to reconnect with, appreciate, and preserve Filipino culture and history. Participant 5 shared, *“Digital, because in digital I can view what really happening in the story, unlike traditional I’m just imagining.”* Another participant added, *“The most valuable platforms is the digital, because we can see, we can imagine, we can hear what will happen to the stories and we can feel it and understand.”* Participant 4 expressed, *“Sa akon liwat as a Gen Z, mas maupay kasi siya pag sa video like YouTube. Mayda kasi gehapon ton, kay ha yana tanan mayda na, so, ini nga epics mayda na gehap ini video sa YouTube. Because mas interested hiya tapos ano... maintindihan mo talaga hiya kay ban mafefeel mo gehapon mo hiya* (“For me, as a Gen Z, it’s better when it’s in video form like on YouTube. There are already versions available there, so these epics can also be found on YouTube. It’s more interesting that way and you can really understand it because you can both see and hear it, which also makes you feel it more.”)

These results align with studies showing that digital platforms support cultural preservation and engagement, such as Botangen, Vodanovich, and Yu’s (2018) work on indigenous Igorot culture and Peñalba et al. (2020) findings on digital storytelling in Philippine classrooms. However, some participants still prefer traditional methods; Participant 1 stated, “The Traditional way of

introducing epic stories, values the most because in this way as a reader and listener, I could easily understand the main idea of a story since it was lectured at the same time unlike just reading it through digital platforms." This highlights a tension between digital innovation and the authenticity and depth of traditional pedagogical approaches.

Gen Z Perception on Epics

Generation Z students perceive Philippine historical epics as important cultural vessels that preserve identity, history, and culture. They believe digital media platforms enhance traditional learning methods by making these epics more interactive and engaging. Participant 6 stated, "This digital presentation affects my view of this Philippine historical epics, in the way that we can understand the main point and the context unlike the past that we taught in oral and textbook only that we cannot understand really. Yes, I can see a potential platform because in social media we can post the stories and we can preserve and pass to the next generation." Likewise, participant 5 affirmed, "Through digital representation, I can see epic stories livelier and more interesting. Yes, it preserved literature buy posting it on social media platforms."

These findings align with Tolentino (2014), who highlighted that digital media bridges traditional literature and modern learners by providing spaces for cultural texts to stay relevant.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study found that Gen Z college students only have partial awareness of Philippine historical epics, often recalling well-known stories like *Biag ni Lam-ang* and *Hudhud* from their school lessons.

While the classroom remains an important space for passing down these cultural texts, many students shared that learning through digital media such as YouTube and TikTok makes the stories feel more alive, engaging, and easier to connect with. For them, these platforms do not replace tradition but instead help preserve and sustain interest in the epics in ways that match their generation's habits. This reflects Tolentino's (2014) view that digital media bridges traditional literature and modern learners, and echoes Prensky's (2001) idea that digital natives learn best through interactive and media-rich experiences. Peñalba et al. (2020) also showed how digital storytelling can deepen cultural appreciation in classrooms. Hence, schools are encouraged to blend traditional teaching with digital storytelling, while educators and cultural institutions work together to create high-quality multimedia versions of epics. Government and cultural agencies can also help by promoting these works online to reach more young people. Ultimately, a balance of tradition and technology is key to ensuring that Gen Z not only learns about these epics but also values them as part of their identity and heritage.

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